

X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY CHARACTERISING CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: Continuous C-fibers are used to reinforce light metals. Preforms are made of tows consisting of thousands of fibers arranged unidirectional, in layers of different fiber orientations, or in layers of woven fabrics. The arrangement of C-fiber bundles in aluminum and magnesium matrix composites (CFRM) is revealed non-destructively by X-ray micro-tomography (μ XCT). The low densities of the investigated materials allow to apply X-rays excited between 50 and 80 kV, which provides material contrast between unreinforced and reinforced Mg or Al matrix.

The course of the fiber bundles can be observed by scanning through the reconstructed 3D images of high resolution tomography. Fiber free matrix regions can be depicted by iso-surfaces of the interface towards reinforced sections and their extension can be measured. The gray value histograms of whole samples and segments thereof can be determined quantitatively. Benchmark histograms of CFRM with densely packed fiber arrangements either unidirectional or in textile structures can be specified. A quantitative quality criterion for CFRM samples is defined by the percentage of agreement between their XCT gray value histograms and the benchmark curve of the appropriate composite.

KEYWORDS: non destructive testing, metal matrix composite, fiber distribution, magnesium, aluminum

1. INTRODUCTION

C-fiber reinforcement of light materials is considered, when high specific strength and stiffness are required. Fiber tows are wound or fabrics are stapled to prepare preforms, which are infiltrated by polymers or metals in liquid state. A recent overview on composite materials [1] provides a special volume dedicated to metal matrix composites [2]. The properties of continuous C-fiber reinforced composites are very sensitive to the fiber orientation owing to the reinforcing mechanisms of fibers, but in addition due to the highly anisotropic properties of C-fibers. Unidirectional (UD) C-fiber reinforced metals (CFRM) exhibit improved properties in fiber direction, but degrade the matrix properties in transverse direction [3]. Non-destructive determination of fiber orientation and their three-dimensional (3D) arrangement in the composite provides the structural information for the prediction of CFRM-properties. X-ray tomography (XCT) became an efficient research tool for investigation of heterogeneous materials [4], which is applied to determine non-destructively the C-fiber arrangement in Mg- and Al-matrix composites. Scanning electron and optical micrographs of cross sections are used for interpretation of the reconstructed XCT-images. The exploitation of XCT by high resolution techniques (μ XCT) and for quantitative measures of CFRM quality, as far as fiber arrangement is concerned, will be shown by means of a few examples.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Continuous fiber reinforced light metals (CFRM)

The investigated Mg and Al matrix composites reinforced with continuous C-fibers have been produced by gas pressure infiltration by Leichtmetall-Kompetenzzentrum Ranshofen/Austria (LKR) [5] and Institut für Leichtbau und Kunststofftechnik, TU-Dresden/Germany (ILK) [6] as indicated in

Table 1. Tows of high modulus (M40) fibers had been wound to obtain densely packed UD fiber preforms for 2 mm thick plates. Unidirectional fabrics have been stapled alternatively in $0/\pm 60^\circ$ orientations, whereas $0/90^\circ$ woven fabrics of high strength (T300) fibers parallel to each other. These preforms have been compressed to produce plate-like samples and additional pressure is acting on the fiber bundles by the infiltration front of the non-wetting melt.

Table 1: Specification of investigated metal matrix composites (CFRM)

Acronym	Matrix	C-Fibers	Arrangement	v_f [%]	Source	Dimensions
Al/M40/UD	Al(99.85)	M40B	unidirectional wound	74 ± 3	LKR	Plates
Mg/M40/UD	MgAl0.6	M40	unidirectional wound	70 ± 1	LKR	$150 \times 65 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$
Al/M40/st0/ $\pm 60^\circ$	Al(99.85)	M40B	$[0, 60, 2(-60), 60, 0^\circ]$ staple	64 ± 4	LKR	
Mg/T300/w0/ 90°	MgAl0.2	T300J	$0/90^\circ$ weaves(50%/50%)	55 ± 3	ILK	Rods $15 \times 5 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$

The fiber distribution is observed on polished samples prepared by traditional preparation procedure for both optical and scanning electron microscopy: grinding to the finest grade using methanol or water free lubricant for the Mg matrix CFRM, additional polishing for Al matrix CFRM. The fibers are densely packed in the UD samples yielding up to 77 vol.% locally, where the original fiber tows can hardly be recognized (see Fig. 1), but sometimes there are matrix veins between fiber bundles. Micrographs of CFRM samples with 6 UD fiber layers stapled symmetrically in orientations differing by 60° or 120° are shown in Fig. 2. There are fiber free matrix interlayers between the differently oriented fiber layers, but not between the centrally placed parallel fiber layers. Fig. 3 gives in-plane and cross sectional views of Mg/T300/w0/ 90° (50% in each direction), where the fibers are densely packed within the fiber bundles of the woven fabrics, but the bundles are clearly separated [7].

The overall volume fraction of fibers v_f given in Table 1 was determined from the density ρ_c and the weight W_a of the CFRM, using the fiber density ρ_f specified by the producer and the mass W_f of the reinforcement obtained by dissolution of the matrix by diluted HCl acid: $v_f = (W_f / \rho_f) / (W_a / \rho_c)$. The fibers are densely packed in the UD samples yielding 70 and 74 vol.% for the high modulus fibers in the two matrices. The average volume fraction for the samples with the differently oriented layers is less owing to the matrix interlayers as shown in Fig. 2. The average volume fraction of infiltrated woven fabrics depends on the textile pattern, which reaches $v_f = 55$ vol.% in the investigated Mg/T300/w0/ 90° sample. The packing of high strength fibers is usually less dense than that of high modulus fibers.

The determination of volume fractions of fibers by image analysis faces the difficulty that the magnification has to be high enough to image the fiber-matrix interfaces of densely packed fibers of ca. $7 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter each. Consequently a statistical number of pictures has to be analysed to obtain an average volume fraction for the sample. That can be done reasonably well for densely packed UD samples with an accuracy of $\pm 3\%$, but it becomes a systematic problem for layered and textile preforms [7]. The volume fractions within the 6 fiber layers of the Al/M40/st0/ $\pm 60^\circ$ sample (disregarding veins) have been determined by image analysis as indicated in Fig. 2a. The volume fraction within the fiber bundles of Mg/T300/w0/ 90° is ca. 65 vol% in average ranging from 60 to 75 vol% in the bundles' center. The quantification of the local variations in fiber distribution by microscopy of cross sections of CFRM is destructive and very laborious, especially due to veins in between some fiber bundles.

2.2 X-ray computed microtomography (μXCT)

Microtomography is based on the same physical principals and mathematical algorithms as the classical medical XCT-scanners as shown in Fig. 4a. A complete set of 2-dimensional X-ray radiographs of the object is recorded from different angular directions. For practical reasons, image detector and source are held in a fixed position and the sample is rotated. Cross section images are created using a filtered back-projection algorithm with convolution and correction for fan beam [8].

Figure 1: Optical micrographs of cross sections of unidirectional C-fiber reinforced composites showing matrix veins between some fiber bundles: (a) Al/M40/UD; (b) Mg/M40/UD

Figure 2: SEM pictures of Al/M40/st0,±60° showing (a) the cross section of the 6 layers with their fiber orientation and volume fraction; (b) Al interlayer between layer #1 and #2.

Figure 3: Optical micrographs of Mg/T300/w0/90° with stapled 0/90° (50%/50%) woven C-fiber fabric layers: (a) in plane, (b) cross-section.

Figure 4: (a) Diagram showing the micro-focus X-ray source, the turning sample and the high resolution area detector. (b) X-ray absorption coefficients of the constituents of the investigated CFRM calculated with XCOM [10].

The reconstructed cross sections from all layers contain full 3D information about the object's internal morphology without special sample preparation or treatment. The method is limited to light weight materials and small dimensions, because the sample must be sufficiently transparent for X-rays of the available energy.

Recording of the images was made using the SkyScan-1072 high-resolution desk-top microtomograph [9]. This instrument has a warranted resolution of about $8\mu\text{m}$ and under favorable conditions a detail detectability down to $3\mu\text{m}$. The system contains a sealed air cooled X-ray microfocus source 20-80kV and a 2D cooled CCD detector with 1024×1024 pixels/12bit and pixel-size of $12\mu\text{m}$. The scintillator is coupled with a 2:1 reduction fiber optics, such that the total field of view is 25 millimeters. Magnification of the sample is obtained by projection of a "shadow" radiograph onto the detector. According to the general rule for tomographic reconstruction, the object should always remain inside the field of view of the X-ray cone. Hence the final resolution (voxel size) depends on the maximum diameter of the object: the resolution of $8\mu\text{m}$ is limited by the X-ray source for objects $<10\text{mm}$, whereas for objects $>12\text{mm}$ the resolution of the order of $25\mu\text{m}$ is limited by the detector.

The X-ray absorption coefficient for the constituents of the CFRM investigated depends on the X-rays' energy as shown in Fig. 4b [10]. The difference in absorption allows to distinguish between materials by discrimination of intensities transformed into gray values. Below 3 keV most of the X-rays are absorbed by the Be window of the X-ray tube. The spectral composition is shifted to the hard side of the spectrum, when the polychromatic beam penetrates the sample. The result is an apparent higher density at the rim of the sample, which causes the well known artifact of "beam hardening" [8]. This effect can be largely reduced by incorporation of an 0.8mm Al filter eliminating practically all X-rays below 15 keV, by using the standard SkyScan correction procedure based on actual transmission measurement on Al and by adjustments minimizing the cupping effect.

2.3 Three dimensional characterization of CFRM

The μXCT -recordings of the CFRM have been performed mostly at 50 kV and 100 μA current. The composite sample was scanned simultaneously with reference samples: commercially pure Al and Mg; a graphite electrode of 1.415g/cm^3 density, the porosity of which cannot be resolved by μXCT . The manufacturer of the fiber material gives a density of 1.77g/cm^3 , less than 2.26g/cm^3 of graphite. After reconstruction of the μXCT images, all reference materials gave a gaussian gray value distribution (see Fig. 7a). There remains some uncertainty regarding the linearity of the grayscale. At a scale where air is set to 0, the mean gray values of the reference samples were determined at 205 for pure Al

Figure 5: μ XCT sections through an Al/M40/st0, \pm 60° sample (0° fiber direction 15° inclined to the specimen edge), showing 6 fiber layers with Al interlayers, various veins in the different layers, a crack parallel to the fibers in #6, irregular fiber distribution in #1.

Figure 6: Mg/T300/w0/90° sample region with missing fiber bundles: (a) iso-surface reconstruction from μ XCT of the fiber free matrix region, (b) optical micrograph of a cross section.

and at 29 for the electrode material, which was corrected to 37 for the higher density of C-fibers. An Al-sample containing 75 vol.% unidirectional densely packed C-fibers provides a benchmark histogram for CFRM of 2g/cm³ mass density.

The example of a μ XCT reconstruction given in Fig. 5 consists of 6 selected cross sections along an Al/M40/st0, \pm 60° sample of 15 \times 5 \times 2 mm³, which has been cut 15° inclined to the fiber directions of layers #1 and #6. Matrix agglomerations between the differently oriented fiber layers (Al interlayers) and between fiber bundles (veins) can be seen as well as a crack running in the top layer #6, both parallel to the fibers. Some of the veins disappear along the sample. The absence of an Al interlayer between the parallel layers #3 and #4 is confirmed. Layer #1 exhibits irregular fiber free matrix and a disordered fiber arrangement. One sample of Mg/T300/w0/90° contains fiber layers ending within the sample as shown in Fig. 6. The intensities of 3D μ XCT recordings can be discriminated between the absorption by the fiber free and reinforced matrix. The interface between the two regions was computed providing an iso-surface of the absorption contour of fiber-free Mg-matrix as depicted in Fig. 6a. In this way the shape of inhomogenities like fiber free regions and veins can be visualized in 3D.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Fiber packing

The quality of fiber packing of UD fiber reinforced metals can be quantified by comparison of the gray value histograms of CFRM samples with a benchmark curve, an example of which is shown in Fig. 7a for 2 layers of the Al/M40/st0, \pm 60° sample (see Fig. 5). The benchmark histogram is matched to the height of the gray value histogram of the test sample giving a corresponding histogram area B. Subtracting B from the area of the measured curve A yields the area beyond the benchmark distribution: $E = A - B$, related to the total area of the gray value histogram of the sample in consideration gives $D = E/A$, the relative deviation from a perfect densely packed CFRM. The difference $P = 1 - D$ indicates the degree of perfection in fiber packing. The packing quality P, expressed in % of the benchmark distribution, is given for layer #3 with 100% and for layer #1 with 78% in Fig. 7a.

Figure 7: Gray value histograms: (a) reference samples of constituents Al and C; B benchmark UD Al-CFRM with 75 vol.% of C-fibers (identical with layer #3 of Al/M40/st0, \pm 60°) compared with A of layer #1 yields P=78%. (b) Histograms of the whole sample Al/M40/st0, \pm 60° (P=75%), layers #1-3 (lower half: P=67%) and layers #4-6 (upper half: P=83%); inserted cross

section of the Al/M40/st0, $\pm 60^\circ$ sample recorded by μ XCT.

The whole Al/M40/st0,±60° sample can be validated by calculating P with respect to a perfect UD-CFRM. Fig. 7b gives the gray value distribution of the sample and the matched benchmark curve. The exceeding tail due to matrix interlayers and veins amounts to D=25% of that histogram. The packing quality of the whole sample is P=75%, the portion equivalent to densely packed UD-CFRM. An important quality criterion of planar samples is the symmetry of fiber arrangement in thickness with respect to the central plane. The μ XCT data can be divided by the central plane and the two halves compared. Fig. 7b shows the histograms of the lower (layers #1-#3) and the upper half (layers #4-#6), with packing qualities of 67% and 83%, respectively. This considerable difference makes this CFRM sample behave like a bi-metal during temperature changes owing to the resulting local difference in thermal expansion [11].

3.2 Matrix layers in stapled fiber reinforcements

The matrix interlayers in CFRM reinforced by stapled textiles can be quantified by integrating the gray levels over planes parallel to the fibers as indicated in Fig. 8. The distance between the resulting density maxima gives the average thickness of each fiber layer D_s . There is no significant interlayer between layer #3 and #4, because both have the same fiber orientation. Layer #6 is the most densely packed of about 300 μm thickness. The deviation of layer #1 from perfect packing can be locally quantified: The matrix accumulation increases gradually towards the sample's surface. The peak areas can be compared with a theoretical step function of fiber free aluminum (μ_{Al}) above the background level of the CFRM (μ_{MMC}) yielding a width for the same area of the measured curve above the CFRM background level, which represents the average thickness of the matrix interlayers D_{Al} as given in Fig. 8. 16 μm seems to be the minimum value achievable between different fiber orientations in this lay up system. More than 10% of the sample's thickness are occupied by the matrix interlayers.

Figure 8: Average density profile of the x/z -planes of μ XCT of the Al/M40/st0,±60° sample as indicated in the insert (compare Fig. 5): peaks at the Al interlayers, the areas of which are equal to the rectangles $(\mu_{\text{Al}} - \mu_{\text{MMC}}) \cdot D_{\text{Al}}^{(i)}$, providing the indicated thickness values. The distances between the peaks yield the average thickness of the fiber layers $D_s^{(i)}$.

3.3 Distribution of woven fiber reinforcement

CFRM reinforced by woven textile fabrics contain fiber free matrix adjacent to each bundle cross over. Fig. 9a/b illustrates in plane and cross sectional μ XCT gray value distribution of a Mg/T300/w0/90° sample. The bright areas of matrix accumulations can be observed in the different views. The fiber arrangement in this sample looks very dense and regular. Fig. 9c shows that the histogram for woven reinforcements corresponds to a packing quality $P = 78\%$ with respect to densely packed UD-CFRM (Mg/M40/UD with $v_f = 70\%$), which corresponds to the determined average volume fraction of $0.78 \times 70 \text{ vol.}\% = 55 \text{ vol.}\%$ fibers. Therefore the corresponding histogram of gray values can be taken as benchmark for Mg-samples with reinforcements of woven 0/90° high strength C-fibers. The symmetry check with respect to the central plane gives identical histograms for both halves of the sample confirming the quality of fiber arrangement.

The gray value histogram of an irregular section of a Mg/T300/w0/90° sample depicted in Fig. 6 yields a packing quality of about 40% with respect to UD-CFRM due to the fiber free matrix regions. The comparison with the benchmark histogram of the regular CFRM described in Fig. 9 results in a reinforcement quality of about 50% with respect to regular CFRM with 0/90° weave reinforcements.

Figure 9: Cross-sections (μ XCT at 50 kV) of a perfect Mg/T300/w0/90° sample: (a) parallel to the woven fabric, (b) transverse: dark fiber bundles with bright matrix in between. (c) Histograms of gray values of the whole sample and of the two halves, all of them yielding $P=78\%$ in relation to the inserted benchmark histogram (dashed line) of a densely packed UD CFRM.

4. CONCLUSIONS

X-ray computed tomography allows to visualize non-destructively the course of C-fiber bundles in light metals, which are in dimensions bigger than 0.1 mm. Although μ XCT was applied for samples of a few millimeters yielding a spatial resolution of ca. $10\mu\text{m}$, individual fibers cannot be resolved, but fiber bundles will be resolvable in samples up to diameters of 100 mm. The absorption contrast between Al and C is high enough as well as that between C and Mg owing to the photo-electric absorption difference to distinguish unreinforced and reinforced matrix. C-fiber bundles in epoxy matrix can be imaged as well.

The course of the fiber bundles can be depicted non-destructively by μ XCT owing to the bundle structure replicated by the matrix. The fiber orientation can be determined as well as veins and cracks wider than one voxel. Fiber free regions can be discriminated and their contours can be depicted by iso-surfaces. In analogy regions of poor infiltration by the matrix can be identified as well and imaged as iso-surface. Fiber or matrix free regions can be quantified by the occupying volume fraction of the sample. The average thickness of interlayers in between fiber layups can be calculated as well as maxima or minima can be localized in XCT recordings. Metallographic pictures give only a local impression of the non-uniformity, whereas XCT provides quantitative 3D information. The iso-surface technique can be applied to present the interface in selectively reinforced components.

The quality of fiber distribution within a volume of CFRM can be quantified by gray value histograms, which consist of the contribution of CFRM of different volume fractions of reinforcement up to fiber free matrix. If pores or cracks bigger than a few voxels existed, small gray levels would be identified as well. Densely packed unidirectional reinforced matrix provides histograms which can serve as a benchmark, when the fiber distribution is verified by metallography and the fiber volume fraction calibrated by matrix dissolution. The deviation of histograms from benchmark curves provides a quantitative measure of the correspondence to a perfect CFRM. Such benchmark histograms can be established for different fiber arrangements to serve as a quality criterion. The analysis of the packing quality of a CFRM can be made for the whole sample as well as for segments of a sample to verify uniformity.

Especially in the stage of development of a CFRM component μ XCT can serve as a tool for non-destructive determination of fiber arrangements before testing. In the course of production the specification of benchmark histograms can provide quantitative quality criteria, which in an automated process could be applied for online control. A study on the applicability to C-fiber reinforced polymers is in progress.

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